

ANIMA

Aviation Noise Impact Management
through Novel Approaches

D3.7 Dynamic Noise Maps and Social Media Analysis: novel technologies for noise impact assessment

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 769627

Project Information	
PROJECT ID	769627
PROJECT FULL TITLE	Aviation Noise Impact Management through Novel Approaches
PROJECT ACRONYM	ANIMA
FUNDING SCHEME	RIA – Research and Innovation action
START DATE OF THE PROJECT	01.10.2017
DURATION	48 months
CALL IDENTIFIER	H2020-MG-2017-SingleStage-INEA
PROJECT WEBSITE	www.anima-project.eu
Deliverable Information	
DELIVERABLE N° AND TITLE	D3.7 Dynamic Noise Maps and Social Media Analysis: novel technologies for noise impact assessment
TYPE OF DELIVERABLE¹	R
DISSEMINATION LEVEL²	PU; Annex1 CO
BENEFICIARY NUMBER AND NAME	21 – Universite de Cergy Pointoise
AUTHORS	Nico van Oosten, Emir Ganić, Dimitris Kotzinos, Asma Gharbi, Catherine Lavandier
CONTRIBUTORS	
WORK PACKAGE N°	WP3
WORK PACKAGE LEADER	Roalt Aalmoes
WP LEADER VALIDATION DATE	11.12.2021
COORDINATOR VALIDATION DATE	13.12.2021
COORDINATOR SIGNATURE	

¹ Use one of the following codes: R=Document, report (excluding the periodic and final reports)

DEM=Demonstrator, pilot, prototype, plan designs

DEC=Websites, patents filing, press & media actions, videos, etc.

OTHER=Software, technical diagram, etc.

² Use one of the following codes: PU=Public, fully open, e.g. web

CO=Confidential, restricted under conditions set out in Model Grant Agreement

CI=Classified, information as referred to in Commission Decision 2001/844/EC.

Version follow-up		
Update	Name	Version
10.11.2021	Asma Gharbi Emir Ganić	V01
30.11.2021	Dimitris Kotzinos	V02
09.12.2021	Dimitris Kotzinos	V03

TABLE OF CONTENTS

Executive Summary	6
1. Dynamic Noise Maps	7
1.1 Background and definition	7
1.2 Human mobility patterns	8
1.2.1 Different ways of collecting human mobility patterns	8
1.2.2 Challenges of capturing human mobility patterns	9
1.3 Methodology	10
1.3.1 Daily mobility patterns of population	10
1.3.2 Aircraft noise contour modelling	11
1.3.3 Calculation of dynamic noise maps	12
1.4 ANIMA Case Study: Dynamic Noise Maps for Ljubljana Airport	15
1.4.1 Study design and input data	15
1.4.2 Results	21
1.4.3 Conclusion	25
1.5 Possible improvements and lessons learnt	26
2. Social Media Analysis	28
2.1 Context	28
2.2 Scientific Background	30
2.2.1 Machine Learning-based Approach	30
2.2.2 Lexicon-based Approach	31
2.2.3 Hybrid Approach	31
2.3 Analysis Pipeline	32
2.4 Lexicon-based Opinion Classification	33
2.4.1 Collection and Preprocessing of Tweets	33
2.4.2 Relevance Detection	33
2.4.3 Sentiment Analysis of Relevant Tweets	34
2.4.4 Experimental Evaluation	34
2.4.5 Analysis of results	35
2.5 Machine Learning and Embeddings-based Opinion Classification	37
2.5.1 Collection and Preprocessing of Tweets	37
2.5.2 Relevance Detection	37
2.5.3 Sentiment Analysis of Relevant Tweets	39
2.5.4 Word Sentiment Score calculation	39
2.5.5 Tweet Sentiment score calculation	40
2.5.6 Clustering-Based Sentiment Classification	40

2.6	<i>Evaluation and Results</i>	42
2.6.1	Relevance Detection	42
2.6.2	Sentiment Analysis.....	43
2.7	<i>Conclusions</i>	49
References		50

Executive Summary

Deliverable 3.7 is focusing on novel methods to account, measure and possibly understand and explain people's annoyance from airport activities that produce noise. We focus on the ability to calculate two types of information that would help the assessment of the annoyance.

We firstly work on the calculation of dynamic noise maps, acoustic maps that illustrate in real time the temporal change of noise levels. We introduce in these noise maps calculations that are based on the mobility patterns of the individuals. In this deliverable, different ways of collecting human mobility patterns will be explained in more details along with the methodology used to incorporate it into dynamic noise maps. Furthermore, a real case study conducted within the ANIMA project, based on the one-year air traffic data, sheds light on the benefits of using this new approach and demonstrate how daily movements influence the estimated population noise annoyance around an airport. The work uses daily mobility patterns to assess the impact on people and more specifically the number of people that have been annoyed /affected on a daily basis. Real world scenarios for Ljubljana and Heathrow airports are considered and discussed. The Heathrow airport case study described in Annex 1 is confidential and will be publicly available upon publication of these results.

On the other hand, we try to measure and understand the annoyance as it is expressed by people who are living in the area on social media posts. We capture and analyse millions of such posts and classify them based on their polarity. It is by itself an interesting research problem to be able to define the notion of positive (no or minimal annoyance) and negative (high levels of annoyance) sentiments that people carry in those posts. We exploit in this study the ability to capture a significant amount of information, which has the potential to allow us to break free from the limitations of traditional surveying methods. On the other hand, further research is necessary into accounting for the biases already existing on the internet. Thus, in this part of the study, we restrict ourselves into conclusions that can be drawn by comparing the collected data after the classification process (aka among itself) and no generalization to the general public is attempted. The study aims to create a prototype and assess the feasibility of the task of understanding people's annoyance based on social media posts and it does not try to provide final conclusions on this. We do this by relying to a set of Machine Learning (ML) and Artificial Intelligence (AI) tools, which we train and use to learn from the data. While the main goal of the current work is to explore the sentiment as positive or negative, the effort could be further expanded to extract additional semantics. Furthermore, the work described here is based on two independent methods to assess social media posts in both real-time and offline. We plan to release these tools as a comprehensive open-source toolkit to be usable by any researcher.

The advances in computational technology and the advanced ability to capture data, being mobility habits or social media activity, provide us with a unique environment that allows to better understand the effect of airport related activities to the life of people in a non-intrusive and scientifically sound way. This deliverable captures two such efforts, supported by diverse case studies in different countries and demonstrates that additional insights are possible.

1. Dynamic Noise Maps

1.1 Background and definition

Dynamic noise mapping represents a relatively new concept in the airport noise literature. Different authors have used this term for various purposes in the previous years. Before going into further details, it is beneficial to compare the current usage of this term and to precisely define the meaning of the "dynamic noise maps" concept in ANIMA project.

Most of the research studies have used this term to present noise in a given moment of time, i.e. to differentiate between noise maps for different period of the day (peak or off-peak hours) and for the different days of the week (weekdays and weekends) (Kozielecki & Czyzewski, 2008; Mishra, Nair, Kumar, & Shukla, 2021). Another research project ("DYNAMAP," 2014) defines dynamic noise maps as acoustic maps that illustrate in real time the temporal change of noise levels. Such noise maps are constantly updated using algorithms and software in real time for different operating conditions (sources, traffic, and weather conditions), by detecting noise and meteorological data from low-cost monitoring stations and weather sensors (Benocci et al., 2019).

When real-time noise levels obtained from noise monitoring stations are used for dynamic noise mapping, measurements could be taken only at specific points due to limitations in the number of noise monitors. To obtain the existing noise levels for the rest of the area of interest some estimates are needed. This is usually done by updating the previously calculated noise levels using a reverse engineering method (based on a sound power assigned to each existing noise source and the distance to the measuring point) (Simón Otegui et al., 2019).

In several research studies, production of dynamic noise maps has been performed by including the citizens into the process of collecting the noise levels data in their surroundings instead of using noise monitoring stations. In that sense, citizens act as sensors and measure the level of noise using applications on their mobile phone or some other smart device (D'Hondt, Stevens, & Jacobs, 2013; Drosatos, Efraimidis, Athanasiadis, Stevens, & D'Hondt, 2014; Poslončec-Petrić, Šlabek, & Frangeš, 2016).

Although the ultimate goal of making any noise map should be to determine the number of people exposed to noise, none of the mentioned approaches consider the dynamics of population movement. Even though such dynamic noise maps indicate different noise levels during the observed periods for which they are made, it is assumed that the population is constant in all observed locations, which is not the case in reality.

The first attempt to include the dynamics of population's movements into the assessment of aircraft noise exposure was carried out by (Ganić & Babić, 2017), followed by a series of papers by (Ganić, Babić, Čangalović, & Stanojević, 2017, 2018; Ganić, Ho-Huu, Babić, & Hartjes, 2018) and (Ho-Huu, Ganić, Hartjes, Babić, & Curran, 2019). In all this research efforts, the emphasis was on optimising the aircraft assignment to departure and arrival routes, while dynamic noise maps were created only for one-day scenarios to demonstrate the possibilities of the developed algorithm to reduce noise annoyance and fuel consumption. Furthermore,

the calculations of daily population mobility included many assumptions and were based only on data from census.

In this deliverable, different ways of collecting human mobility patterns will be explained in more details along with the methodology used to incorporate it into dynamic noise maps. Furthermore, a real case study conducted within the ANIMA project, based on the one-year air traffic data, sheds light on the benefits of using this new approach and demonstrate how daily movements influence the estimated population noise annoyance around an airport.

1.2 Human mobility patterns

In the sense of dynamic noise mapping, human mobility patterns (sometimes also referred to as population daily mobility or movement patterns) are defined as the movements of human beings (individuals as well as groups) in space and time. Motivation behind people's movements on a daily basis is manifold. While most commonly daily trips include commuting to and from work or school, they are also connected with the social, leisure and other activities.

During the last decade, substantial progress has been made in the study of human mobility. Not only that significant advancement in the field of information and communication technologies enabled more accurate tracking of people's movements, but also collection and processing of such data is more accessible to the general public.

While geography might be the first discipline to analyse mobility data and put forward corresponding theories to describe travel patterns (Barbosa et al., 2018), the study of human mobility currently spans several disciplines. It is widely used in transportation studies to describe how people plan and schedule their daily travel, as well as to provide better forecasts of future travel patterns.

A better understanding of human mobility patterns leads to more appropriate urban planning and infrastructure design, new tools to monitor health and well-being in cities, reduction of pollution, internal security and epidemic modelling, to name but a few. In the ANIMA project, the special emphasis will be given on the use of human mobility patterns to estimate more accurately the number of people annoyed by aircraft noise.

1.2.1 Different ways of collecting human mobility patterns

Collection of information on human mobility has a long tradition. Some of the well-known and widely used techniques to collect the data include surveys and questionnaires. Namely, census data, collected periodically through national surveys, contain the questions related to the location of the workplace and school/faculty as well as the place of residence. By creating an origin-destination matrix, these data can be used to estimate daily/weekly commuting flows within a city or on a country level.

Another way of using questionnaires for collecting the mobility data is by conducting National travel surveys which have proved to be valuable for modelling and planning of transport systems. Compared to the census data, travel surveys contain more detailed information about daily activities of persons participating in the survey, including number of trips per day,

origin and destination of each trip, time of the beginning of each trip, travel time and distance of each trip, purpose of a trip, mode of transport, etc. By using proven statistical methods, data collected through travel surveys allow us to simulate the movements of the whole population with great detail.

Due to technological development and the increase in usage of the internet, the methods to obtain the data have changed through the years, though the purpose mainly remained the same. Digital footprints produced by people using various digital services such as mobile phones, smartphone applications, or social networks, could provide valuable insights into their daily movement patterns.

These digital footprints can be classified as passive and active (Girardin, Calabrese, Fiore, Ratti, & Blat, 2008). The main difference between them is whether they are left voluntary or involuntary. Many online activities such as tweeting or tagging a photo carry an information (electronic trail) about the location and timestamp that could be used to track the movement of the users when the frequency of such activities is satisfactory. Passive footprints are collected involuntarily by using smart-card data, mobile phone records, GPS data, while active footprints come from the users themselves when they expose locational data in photos or messages while using social networks such as Twitter, Facebook or Foursquare and photo-sharing web sites, like Flickr or Instagram.

1.2.2 Challenges of capturing human mobility patterns

All above-mentioned methods can be used to collect population mobility data necessary to develop dynamic noise maps. Nevertheless, numerous challenges can be encountered mostly due to privacy issues. Therefore, any data must be collected in accordance with the legislative framework, such as General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) that harmonises data privacy laws across Europe.

Since microdata from National travel surveys consist of sets of records containing information on individual persons, households, or business entities, they are in most cases confidential with restricted access to protect the anonymity of individual persons or businesses. While there are some microdata sets publicly available, the usual procedure for granting access takes 8-10 weeks and includes signing a Confidentiality agreement and Declaration on Data Protection by the person who will use the microdata.

While travel survey data are accurate but with low sampling rate, mobile phone Call Detail Records (CDRs) have the opposite characteristics and can encompass much longer periods of sampling over larger fractions of the population. Nevertheless, the price for such datasets is in the range of several tens of thousands of euros just for one airport case study. On top of the high price, additional issue with gathering data from mobile phones is the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) that harmonises data privacy laws across Europe. Even though only anonymised user data are required for dynamic noise maps, many mobile phone operators are reluctant to provide access to their data for fear of violating the provisions of the GDPR regulation.

1.3 Methodology

1.3.1 Daily mobility patterns of population

To understand how population movement can influence the noise exposure experienced by individuals (i.e. the noise dose) as they travel during the day, it is necessary to collect data about daily mobility patterns of the population. Developing an adequate travel model is a first step to be able to assess the daily mobility patterns of the population. Some broad types of models used in transportation planning include the following (Castiglione, Bradley, & Gliebe, 2014): sketch-planning models, strategic-planning models, trip-based models, and activity-based models.

The choice of model depends on the purpose for which it will be used. Because activity-based models typically function at the level of individual persons and represent how these persons travel across the entire day, they are most suitable for dynamic noise maps. Since detailed explanation of the activity-based travel models goes beyond the scope of this work, only some brief description of the main concept will be given herein. For more details, interested readers may refer to (Castiglione et al., 2014).

Activity-based models are used to simulate activity patterns that represent activity travel decisions of households and individuals. These activity patterns are composed of many smaller, often related decisions, such as at what time to depart home for work in the morning, what mode of transport to take, whether to make an extra stop for groceries on the way home, and where to make that stop. Other longer-term decisions also have a bearing on activity and travel, such as the choices where to work, where to live, how many cars to own, and whether or not to participate in an employer's transit pass program (Castiglione et al., 2014).

The structure of activity-based models varies in the literature. Nevertheless, between the model inputs and outputs, most activity-based models include the following major types of components (Castiglione et al., 2014): synthetic population, longer-term and mobility choices, daily activity patterns, tour and trip details, and trip assignment.

The first component, synthetic population, represents a basis for predicting the behaviour of the households and persons in the modelled area. It contains anonymous microdata with the appropriate variables and granularity, statistically equivalent to the actual population of interest, to serve as input for micro-simulation agent-based models.

Next component involves modelling of choices that are made on a less frequent, longer-term basis, such as where to live, work or study. In addition, decisions whether to own a car, driving license, bicycles or transit passes also belong to longer-term and mobility choices that can significantly influence the availability and attractiveness of different location, mode, and scheduling choices that create daily activity and travel patterns. These choices are simulated for each agent in the synthetic population.

Conditional upon predicted longer-term and mobility choices, all travels during the day are simulated using day-pattern, tour-level, and trip-level models. The main output of the daily activity pattern model is the exact number of tours that each individual makes for each of a

number of different activity and tour purposes. Scheduling, location choice, and mode choice are all relevant at both the tour level and the trip level.

Scheduling model within the tour predicts the departure and arrival times for mandatory purposes (such as work or school), while the trip-level models simulate additional stops within the tour, for example on the way home, for other non-mandatory purposes (such as shopping, social visits, recreation, etc.).

Apart from the usual home and work/school locations that are predicted within the longer-term and mobility models, location model is used to predict the location of any intermediate stops along the tour, as well as tour origin and the tour destination.

Mode choice model predicts the use of mode at both the tour level and the trip level. In most cases, people are inclined to use the same mode for an entire tour, where the selected mode is the same for each trip within the tour. Nevertheless, there are also infrequent cases of multimodal tours which could include carpooling or park-and-ride concepts.

The final step in the activity-based travel modelling is to assign simulated trips to the networks. The whole process could be iterated to recalculate the travel times or some other parameters, if needed.

As previously discussed, data for assessing a population's daily mobility patterns may come from a variety of sources, such as population census or dedicated household or travel surveys. In addition, digital footprints of inhabitants that use different digital services (mobile phones, smart phone applications, social networks, etc.) could also be used for model development or for its validation (McArdle, Furey, Lawlor, & Pozdnoukhov, 2014; McArdle, Lawlor, Furey, & Pozdnoukhov, 2012).

In this research we use actual travel patterns on the individual level obtained from a daily passenger mobility survey. For each participant in the survey, the data available include: municipality of work/school location and whether the person is working from home or not, number of trips per day, start time for each trip, travel time, distance and purpose of each trip, mode of transport, car ownership status, vehicle occupancy, etc.

To increase the level of detail beyond municipality level, an algorithm is used to assign the exact location within the municipalities for each trip by considering the number of buildings and their actual usage within the defined smaller cell (grid). This means that if a person conducts a trip with an educational purpose, the exact location, represented as cell's centroid, will be assigned to that person based on the number of buildings intended for educational purposes (schools, universities, etc.) within different cells in that particular municipality; the cells containing more buildings are more likely to be selected. The same goes for other trip purposes and buildings. As a result, the time each individual spends (in minutes) within each cell during the day has been calculated.

1.3.2 Aircraft noise contour modelling

To be able to conduct the noise calculations, a noise model needs to be created. Input data for noise modelling that need to be collected consist of yearly air traffic data including

information about origin and destination, aircraft type, actual take-off and arrival time, and runway in use. Ground track data representing departure and arrival routes and flight profiles need to be modelled as well and could be obtained through radar/ADS-B data or Standard Instrument Departure (SID) and Standard Arrival Routes (STAR). Distribution of operations per each runway, aircraft type, route and time of day needs to be assessed. In addition, meteorological data such as headwind speed, pressure, air temperature, and relative humidity, as well as topographical data, could also influence the shape of noise contours. More about modelling aircraft noise could be found in ECAC Doc 29 (ECAC, 2016).

1.3.3 Calculation of dynamic noise maps

After creating noise model and obtaining daily mobility patterns of the population, the next step is to extract the distribution of people at a desired spatial and temporal resolution. The most detailed spatial resolution would include every single location where people spend time. Nevertheless, such a detailed approach is neither practical nor needed for airport noise impact studies since aircraft noise levels do not differ significantly among closely located points. Another approach is to aggregate points into grid cells (e.g. 500 m x 500 m) and to calculate noise levels only at the cells' centroids which will then represent all the points within that cell.

As for the temporal resolution, it will depend on the change in the number of people at different locations and frequency of activities in the observed model. The minimum temporal detail should include at least four or five time periods in the day, as opposed to some models that use continuous time. Furthermore, the temporal resolution could be observed separately for working and non-working days, since these population's daily mobility patterns could be different from one another. As explained above, here we will use temporal resolution in minutes (e.g. 1,440 one-minute periods in the day).

The noise metric that needs to be calculated for each location is the $L_{Aeq,T}$ or the A-weighted, equivalent continuous sound level determined over the time period T . After calculating L_{Aeq} noise levels, the next step is to match the number of people exposed to those noise levels at each location (spatial resolution) during each time period (temporal resolution) and calculate the cumulative noise impact for each person. The two most important indicators defined by the Environmental Noise Directive 2002/49/EC used to determine exposure to environmental noise from major transport and industry sources are the L_{den} (the day, evening, and night-level indicator designed to assess annoyance) and the L_{night} (the night-level indicator designed to assess sleep disturbance). With Eq. 1.1 we determine $L_{den,j}$ for each person j by taking into account that within each hour people might spend different amounts of time (t_{jlt}) at different locations that are exposed to different yearly average noise levels ($L_{Aeq,1h_{lt}}$):

$$L_{den_j} = 10 \cdot \log_{10} \left(\frac{1}{T} \left(\sum_{l \in L} \sum_{t \in T_d} t_{jlt} \cdot 10^{\frac{LA_{eq,1h_{lt}}}{10}} + \sum_{l \in L} \sum_{t \in T_e} t_{jlt} \cdot 10^{\frac{LA_{eq,1h_{lt}}+5}{10}} + \sum_{l \in L} \sum_{t \in T_n} t_{jlt} \cdot 10^{\frac{LA_{eq,1h_{lt}}+10}{10}} \right) \right), \forall j \quad (1.1)$$

where $LA_{eq,1h_{lt}}$ is the A-weighted, equivalent continuous sound level determined over one hour at the location l during the time period t ; t_{jlt} is the amount of time that each person j has spent at the location l during the time period t ; T_d , T_e and T_n represent day (12 hours), evening (4 hours) and night periods (8 hours) as stated in the Environmental Noise Directive 2002/49/EC, while T is equal to 24 hours.

The night time noise indicator L_{night_j} for each person j can be calculated by Eq. 1.2:

$$L_{night_j} = 10 \cdot \log_{10} \left(\frac{1}{T_n} \left(\sum_{l \in L} \sum_{t \in T_n} t_{jlt} \cdot 10^{\frac{LA_{eq,1h_{lt}}}{10}} \right) \right), \forall j \quad (1.2)$$

where T_n , t_{jlt} , $LA_{eq,1h_{lt}}$ have the same meaning as explained for the L_{den_j} . Night time period usually lasts eight hours, starting from 10 PM to 6 AM or from 11 PM to 7 AM.

In order to assess the expected annoyance and harmful effects of aircraft noise upon population, dose-effect relation is used, concerning the following:

- the relation between annoyance and L_{den} for air traffic noise,
- the relation between sleep disturbance and L_{night} for air traffic noise.

From noise levels obtained for each person L_{den_j} , the total number of people annoyed by aircraft noise (NPA) can be estimated using the polynomial approximation in Eq. 1.3 as suggested by the European Commission (European Commission, 2002):

$$NPA = \sum_{j \in J} \left(\left(8.588 \cdot 10^{-6} \cdot (L_{den_j} - 37)^3 + 1.777 \cdot 10^{-2} \cdot (L_{den_j} - 37)^2 + 1.221 \cdot (L_{den_j} - 37) \right) / 100 \right). \quad (1.3)$$

The European Commission also gives the approximation for estimating the total number of people highly annoyed by aircraft noise ($NPHA$) as follows (Eq. 1.4):

$$NPHA = \sum_{j \in J} \left(\left(-9.199 \cdot 10^{-5} \cdot (L_{den_j} - 42)^3 + 3.932 \cdot 10^{-2} \cdot (L_{den_j} - 42)^2 + 0.2939 \cdot (L_{den_j} - 42) \right) / 100 \right). \quad (1.4)$$

The number of people who are sleep-disturbed (NPSD) and the number of people who are highly sleep-disturbed (NPHSD) during the night by air traffic noise can be determined by using L_{night} indicator, as described in the EU-position paper on night time noise (European Commission Working Group on Health and Socio-Economic Aspects, 2004):

$$NPSD = \sum_{j \in J} \left(\left(13.714 - 0.807 \cdot L_{night_j} + 0.01555 \cdot (L_{night_j})^2 \right) / 100 \right) \quad (1.5)$$

$$NPHSD = \sum_{j \in J} \left(\left(18.147 - 0.956 \cdot L_{night_j} + 0.01482 \cdot (L_{night_j})^2 \right) / 100 \right). \quad (1.6)$$

Equation 1.3 indicates that people are supposed to be annoyed by aircraft noise only when the L_{den} values are higher than 37 dB, while people might be highly annoyed if the L_{den} values are higher than 42 dB, as in Eq. 1.4. For the L_{night} indicator, 40 dB was used as the lower limit, as suggested by the World Health Organisation (WHO, 2018).

In March 2020, the new assessment methods for harmful effects have been introduced through Commission Directive (EU) 2020/367 amending Annex III to Directive 2002/49/EC. Member States shall bring into force the laws, regulations, and administrative provisions necessary to comply with this Directive by 31 December 2021 at the latest.

For the calculation of the absolute risk (AR), with respect to the harmful effect of high annoyance (HA) the following dose-effect relations are used for aircraft noise:

$$AR_{HA,air} = (-50.9693 + 1.0168 \cdot L_{den} + 0.0072 \cdot L_{den}^2) / 100 \quad (1.7)$$

For the calculation of the absolute risk, with respect to the harmful effect of high sleep disturbance (HSD) the following dose-effect relations are used for aircraft noise:

$$AR_{HSD,air} = (16.7885 - 0.9293 \cdot L_{night} + 0.0198 \cdot L_{night}^2) / 100 \quad (1.8)$$

The total number of people affected by the harmful effect y (number of attributable cases) due to the aircraft noise, is then:

$$N_y = \sum_j [n_j \cdot AR_{j,y}] \quad (1.9)$$

where $AR_{j,y}$ is the absolute risk of the relevant harmful effect (HA, HSD), and is calculated using the Eq. 1.7 and 1.8, calculated at the central value of each noise band j , while n_j is the number of people that is exposed to the j -th exposure band.

1.4 ANIMA Case Study: Dynamic Noise Maps for Ljubljana Airport

1.4.1 Study design and input data

The case study that will be presented here aims to show how population movements affect the estimated number of people exposed to aircraft noise. The research was done to demonstrate the capabilities of dynamic noise mapping compared to the traditional way of developing noise maps. More information about this study can be found in (Ganić et al., 2020).

Ljubljana Jože Pučnik Airport was chosen for the case study. It is the largest and the busiest international airport in the Republic of Slovenia, located 20 km northwest of the Ljubljana capital. With a single runway 3,300 m long (direction 12/30), the airport handled more than 1.7 million passengers and approximately 31 thousand aircraft operations in 2019. Nevertheless, the year 2018 has been selected based on the availability of data regarding population mobility patterns and air traffic.

Since Ljubljana airport has not reached 50,000 movements per year, preparation of strategic noise maps and action plans according to the implemented EU Directive 2002/49/EC is not mandatory, and neither is the implementation of the Balanced Approach Regulation (EU) 598/2014. Nevertheless, the airport has proactively developed noise contour maps and has been regularly performing continuous noise monitoring in the most noise exposed areas for several years.

1.4.1.1 *Air traffic data*

According to the airport official statistics, yearly traffic for 2018 comprised of 35,512 operations. Departure and arrival routes for each runway were obtained from the ADS-B data provided by OpenSky (<https://opensky-network.org/>), because data for SID and STAR routes were not available from neither the airport nor the ATC, and in many cases could be less accurate, as most aircraft were vectored.

Nine representative routes were selected from the ADS-B data presented in Figure 1.1. There are two departure routes and one arrival route from runway 12, and three departure routes and three arrival routes from runway 30. Departure routes are marked blue, and arrival routes are marked red.

Figure 1.1. Departure (blue) and arrival (red) routes (source: OpenSky, Google Earth)

The fleet mix consisted of 213 different aircraft types. However, to simplify the calculations, the aircraft were classified into groups based on the substitution methodology described in the ICAO Doc 9911 and ECAC Doc. 29 noise modelling guidance using the aircraft substitution tables available in the Aircraft Noise and Performance (ANP) Database. Table 1.1 shows the number of arrival and departure operations for different times of day for 15 aircraft types, which make up to 80% of the total traffic.

Table 1.1. Flight statistics per aircraft type and time of day

ICAO aircraft type code	Day		Evening		Night	
	A	D	A	D	A	D
CRJ9	3586	4674	1284	522	445	117
A319	1302	1542	587	434	305	219
CRJ7	875	1116	305	101	85	48
CRUZ	796	855	79	19	0	0
F100	505	633	137	88	100	21
A320	259	249	262	263	22	29
C172	367	416	84	40	5	0
B734	328	2	3	401	80	8
A320	119	118	72	60	148	162
AT72	369	214	158	350	110	74
L410	66	311	253	6	1	1
DH8D	289	278	2	12	0	1
P28A	239	263	30	6	0	0
SW4	54	260	211	5	0	0
AT75	110	110	132	130	0	2
All others	2709	2868	763	613	119	111
Total	11973	13909	4362	3050	1420	793

A -arrival; D - departure

Figure 1.2 shows the total number of aircraft operations in 2018 for each hour of the day. There are several peaks during the day, while night operations are rare. Most flights are operated between 5 PM and 6 PM with an average value of nine flights per hour during this peak period.

Figure 1.2. Hourly distribution of aircraft operations for year 2018

1.4.1.2 Noise data

Based on the air traffic data provided by Ljubljana airport, The A-weighted equivalent continuous sound level was calculated to match the number of people exposed to those noise levels at each location during each one-hour period. Before calculating the noise data, it is crucial to choose a reasonable number of locations for which the noise data and the population data will be obtained. In this case study, the noise levels were calculated for 18,481 locations, with each location representing the centroid of a 500 m x 500 m grid.

The same grid space has been used to develop population mobility patterns, while for the temporal resolution one-minute periods were used to assess the amount of time each person spends at each grid.

The sound exposure levels (SEL) from which LAeq noise levels were calculated at each location caused by each aircraft type on the different routes are calculated by the SONDEO software. For each operation, the standard ANP profile settings are used. As a result, the cumulative noise impact for each person has been assessed.

In this case study, the total number of people affected by aircraft noise was estimated using the polynomial approximations in equations (1.3)-(1.6) as explained previously. The new assessment methods for harmful effects from March 2020 were not used since they have been introduced after the beginning of this study.

1.4.1.3 Building Cadastre data

Figure 1.3 shows the Real Estate Register and Building Cadastre data provided by the Surveying and Mapping Authority of the Republic of Slovenia (GURS). There are 1,188,949 buildings in Slovenia, out of which 553,357 (46.5%) have a house number. Since each building is divided into parts, in Slovenia there are 1,888,107 building parts. Each part of a building has

its own actual use and there are 59 different actual uses, such as: Residential (872,411), Business (35,584), Commercial (18,216), School and kindergarten (3,445), Museum and library (1,313), Restaurant (8,613), Religious (3,894), Hospital/medical center (553), Bank/post office/insurance company (2,368), Sports Hall (1,928), etc.

Figure 1.3. Real Estate Register and Building Cadastre data
(source: GURS <https://egp.gu.gov.si/egp/>, validity date 22.08.2020)

1.4.1.4 Human mobility patterns

The population mobility patterns are assessed using dedicated national travel survey. The most recent one conducted in Slovenia was the Daily Passenger Mobility Survey (TR-MOB 2017). The data were obtained from the Statistical Office of the Republic of Slovenia through the special request for protected microdata containing detailed information about each trip on an individual level.

Data on daily travel habits, movements and trips were collected for residents aged 15–84 living in Slovenia. The survey examines how many and how (walking or by any other mode of transport) people travel, how much time they spend, and what the trip purpose is (work, education, leisure, shopping, etc.). Data collection took place during the last two weeks in September and in October 2017 which was considered representative period for the entire calendar year (Statistical Office of the Republic of Slovenia, 2019). Equal distribution of working and non-working days was obtained. For more information about this survey, interested readers may refer to methodological explanations given in (Statistical Office of the Republic of Slovenia, 2019). For this case study, we obtained the protected microdata containing detailed information about each trip on an individual level. The number of respondents was 8,842, out of which 1,355 (15.3%) survey participants stayed at home on a selected day, while the other 7,487 persons made 24,195 trips (3.2 trips per day). It is also relevant to mention that 296 (3.3%) persons started their first trip from the municipality other than the municipality where they live.

People tend to choose the start of their trip differently depending on the purpose of the trip. Therefore, there are time periods of the day with pronounced peaks (e.g., early, a.m. peak, midday, p.m. peak, and late) as shown in Figure 1.4. Most of the first-shift workers usually start their trip around 7 a.m. with the pupils and students following the similar trend. The

majority of trips with the purpose of shopping start around 11 a.m. while leisure activities have their peak after 6 p.m.

Figure 1.4. Daily number of trips by trip commencement hour and purpose (source: SURS <https://www.stat.si/statweb>)

Table 1.2 provides short descriptions of each trip purpose along with the number of trips for each purpose for the whole sample. There are seven different purposes of trips, with leisure being most frequent among participants.

Table 1.2. Description and frequency of trip purposes

Trip Purpose	Description	No. of trips
Work (commuting)	Going to work	5871
Professional, business	Business or official errands, business trip up to 300 km	640
Education	Going to school, faculty (education facility)	989
Escorting (of parents)	Driving / picking up/ accompanying a child or other person	2339
Shopping	Visiting stores	3544
Leisure	Visiting friends/relatives, going out to eat or drink, recreational activities (indoor or outdoor), hobbies, walking a pet, working in the garden, sightseeing, visiting cultural or sport events.	8620
Personal business	Health treatment, personal care (e.g. hairdresser), services (e.g. car maintenance), going to the bank, post, religious activities (also funerals).	2192

1.4.2 Results

To assess the influence of daily mobility patterns of the population upon evaluation of aircraft noise effects, noise impact will be presented for each person (dynamic noise maps) and for each location (traditional noise maps). In the first scenario, census data are used to assess the distribution of population to the locations affected by noise, assuming that people stay at their homes for the whole day (24 hours). Since for all currently developed official noise maps such approach is used, this scenario is hereinafter referred to as the reference scenario. On the other hand, if daily mobility patterns of the population are considered, such movements will lead to different distribution of the population during the day and this scenario is hereinafter referred to as the dynamic scenario.

Since the assignment of location for each trip is a stochastic process, 1,000 iterations have been conducted, which improved the precision and statistical significance of the results. As each survey participant represents some portion of the population, we used weights already provided in the TR-MOB 2017 survey to scale up the results and to give a rough estimate of the expected impact on the population. The expected number of people annoyed by aircraft noise is calculated as a sumproduct of noise annoyance (based on the respondent's noise exposure) and weight for each survey respondent. Using the same approach, the results were obtained for highly annoyed, sleep-disturbed and highly sleep-disturbed people for both

scenarios. The average results of 1,000 iterations along with descriptive statistics are presented in Table 1.3.

Table 1.3. Annoyance and sleep disturbance for reference and dynamic scenario

Statistics	Reference scenario				Dynamic scenario			
	NPA	NPHA	NPSD	NPHSD	NPA	NPHA	NPSD	NPHSD
Mean	5430	588	158	92	5588	529	158	91
Median	5435	589	156	90	5588	530	155	90
Min	4756	408	33	19	5058	386	37	22
Max	6227	810	301	174	6226	700	288	167
Range	1471	401	268	155	1168	313	251	145
Standard deviation	202	53	43	25	193	50	43	25

Table 1.3 shows that in the case of the Dynamic scenario, the total number of people annoyed by noise increases by 2.9%, while the number of highly annoyed people decreases by 10% compared to the Reference scenario. This implies that people spend less time during the day in the areas most affected by aircraft noise, while there are more people in less affected areas around the airport. As expected, sleep disturbance indicators do not differ significantly between the two scenarios, since the number of trips during the night is negligible. Reduced number of people who are sleep-disturbed implies that some of the survey participants spent at least some period of the night in the areas outside the noise contours ($L_{\text{night}} > 40$ dB).

What cannot be seen from Table 1.3, however obvious from Figure 1.5 and Figure 1.6, is that different people are affected by aircraft noise than the ones expected. Figure 1.5 shows the difference between the numbers of people annoyed by aircraft noise of the two scenarios for each residential location where the difference exists. The negative difference indicates that for those persons noise impact has been underestimated, since the L_{den} noise levels for the Dynamic scenario are higher than the ones obtained in the Reference scenario or higher than 37 dB if the person does not live within the L_{den} 37 dB noise contours. The positive values suggest that those persons spend more time outside the area of L_{den} 37 dB noise contours during the day and thus the noise impact has been overestimated. Consequently, there is no difference between scenarios for the persons staying home for the whole day.

Figure 1.5. Difference in NPA per location

The L_{den} noise contours caused by all arrival and departure operations are shown in Figure 1.6, where the people affected by aircraft noise at each location are also indicated. At first glance, it can be observed that there are four different types of people in terms of their noise annoyance and location of their residence. The total number of people annoyed by noise (NPA) within the L_{den} noise contours higher than 37 dB for the Reference scenario (marked with red star and white square symbols) is 5,430 as stated in Table 1.3. However, when movements of the people during the day are considered, only 4,884 of them (marked with red star symbol) are annoyed by noise based on the Dynamic scenario. These results lead to the conclusion that even though people live at locations enclosed in the noise contours, 10.1% of them (marked with white square symbol) are not annoyed by aircraft noise due to their daily mobility to locations far away from the airport.

Furthermore, in order to see how many noise annoyed people are located outside the L_{den} noise contours higher than 37 dB, the NPA based on the Dynamic scenario at all locations is evaluated. The results show that, apart from the 4,884 people living within the noise contours, there are additional 704 persons (14.4%) also experiencing noise annoyance (marked with yellow triangles), which in total makes 5,588 people annoyed by noise for the Dynamic scenario (as shown in Table 1.3). This can be explained by considering that people who live outside the area affected by aircraft noise may work or study within these areas at some time during the day and are therefore affected by aircraft noise. The fourth group of people (marked with grey circles) resides outside the noise contours and is not affected by aircraft noise, even when the daily mobility patterns are considered.

Figure 1.6. L_{den} noise contours and people affected by aircraft noise

In order to better demonstrate the dynamics behind this novel approach, four different noise maps with estimated number of people at each location are presented in the Figure 1.7 describing a) night (02-03h), b) morning (08-09h), c) afternoon (14-15h) and d) evening (20-21h) periods. This figure illustrates the temporal and spatial variation in population around Ljubljana airport. In addition, the change in the number of operations between the presented hours is clearly visible through the different shapes and areas that calculated noise contours take. As expected, the smallest changes are observed during night hours, when the traffic frequency is low as well as the movements of the people.

Figure 1.7. Temporal and spatial variation in population noise exposure around Ljubljana airport

It should be bear in mind that this case study only considers L_{den} as a factor for estimating annoyance. As shown within the ANIMA project, aside from noise exposure, non-acoustic factors have a considerable influence on perceived annoyance, and they should also be taken into account in future research on dynamic noise mapping.

1.4.3 Conclusion

In this work, we have considered a particular case study for which we have detailed records for a full Slovenia population sample coming from a mobility survey. The noise impact levels generated by the average Ljubljana airport traffic have been calculated hour per hour and the expected noise annoyance upon the population has been measured considering both the residents and the actively present individuals. The estimated noise annoyance showed that a portion of the most affected population does not spend the whole day in the affected areas. In this case, the neighbourhoods around the airport are mostly residential and few people enter them during working hours. This implies that without taking into account the population's mobility, the number of people annoyed is either overestimated or underestimated. The airport is 20 km away from the capital, where most of the services, educational centres and jobs are concentrated. The population, therefore, travels in and out of the annoyed areas during the day, thus changing their daily noise impact. As expected, if only night disturbance is considered, the difference is much lower, and it is due to the small fraction of the population who move during the night.

As future research, these results must be validated in urban areas that are more diverse in terms of land use. For instance, if logistic, industrial, or commercial areas are concentrated close to an airport, the annoyance may even increase if mobility is considered, since these will be the areas of concentration of the population during the day. Secondly, we divided the time into hour intervals to calculate the noise contours. As long as very detailed mobility data are available, we can refine this calculation to the impact of individual flights. Thirdly, the sample of the population considered must be widened to prevent uncertainty in the metrics and statistical errors. This will be done by including data from other sources, larger surveys or

synthetic population, over which models could be run to study what-if scenarios including mitigation policy actions.

1.5 Possible improvements and lessons learnt

There are several directions for the future development of dynamic noise maps. This includes the involvement and contribution of several stakeholders and interested parties who can influence the collection and quality of necessary data, the adoption of legal frameworks, as well as the management of airport operations, all based on the new knowledge regarding the population noise exposure due to daily migration.

First of all, collecting more detailed data on population daily movements is the basis for a more accurate calculation of the actual exposure of the population to noise. Therefore, encouraging active public involvement, especially of the residents living in the vicinity of the airport, would significantly improve the quality of dynamic noise maps. One of the steps towards achieving this goal is to motivate citizens to contribute through participation in daily mobility surveys or by using dedicated applications that can collect data on people's movements. In that sense, it is pivotal to educate the citizens thus they could understand more clearly the needs of the airport and be more willing to participate in such endeavours. It goes without saying that by giving the necessary and truthful information about their movement patterns, residents are helping the airport to better solve the noise problem they could be faced with. On the other hand, it is also advisable to educate the airport authorities to adopt and take advantage of the new technologies and approaches through which dynamic noise maps can be implemented in practice more easily, taking care however to remain very vigilant on privacy issues.

Although the above-mentioned surveys are mainly organised and conducted by the National Statistical Institutes, usually on a country level, one of the future directions may stimulate airports to also embrace such activities. In that regard, the airport authorities could conduct more detailed and more frequent surveys on a smaller sample, that could primarily include settlements around the airport that are most affected by aircraft noise. In that way, the movement habits of the local residents could be determined more accurately. Estimation of the number of people highly annoyed by aircraft noise, with such new data, could give the airport authorities a new perspective on the noise issue around the airport. Through such dedicated questionnaires, residents could also express their preferences about the periods of the day when the aircraft noise bothers them the most, or vice versa to indicate to the airport when, due to the nature of their activities, noise is not an issue since they could be far away from their residences. If applicable, airports could use such information when negotiating with the airlines about the seasonal schedule in order to reduce annoyance. Certainly, this approach is in line with the modern aspirations of every airport that has a noise issue since the current focus is primarily on improving communication with the residents, sharing information, and providing transparent reporting about the airport noise to the general public.

Air navigation service providers (ANSPs) could also benefit from dynamic noise maps and use them to reduce the adverse impact of noise on the population. The number of people in an

area is a vital indicator for the noise impact analysis and should therefore be considered when making decisions regarding air traffic assignment that influence the noise allocation. Population noise exposure reduction can be achieved by optimising the distribution of aircraft on arrival and departure routes, by considering spatial and temporal variations in the number of inhabitants in the settlements around the airport, since these data are available in dynamic noise maps. One of the future developments of this approach could lead to the inclusion of dynamic noise maps into a decision support tool that could help air traffic controllers in their activities either on operational, tactical, pre-tactical or strategic level. There are several ongoing research efforts in this direction which will allow the ANSPs to minimize the number of people exposed to noise while using the benefits of dynamic noise maps.

Finally, to enforce the dynamic noise maps approach, it is pivotal to involve policymakers who have the power of setting and directing regulatory frameworks that should follow the developments in this area. All current studies conducted on the basis of a legally imputed obligation, as is the case of strategic noise maps, consider the noise level on the most exposed façade of the building. All reported numbers of people exposed to noise are attributed to all persons living in the buildings according to the census data, regardless of their actual location. Future regulatory developments may consider the inclusion of population daily mobility patterns in the noise mapping process in order to assess the impact of noise on the population more realistically. Therefore, it is key to inform policymakers about the possibilities of dynamic noise maps and their advantages compared to traditional noise maps currently in use, on noise today but maybe on local air quality too tomorrow. More detailed research on this topic should provide guidelines on how to incorporate this approach into the legislation so that any airport that has a noise problem could benefit from a dynamic noise mapping approach.

2. Social Media Analysis

2.1 Context

Online social media provide access to a massive amount of information. Connecting people from all over the world, they enable them to share daily news and express their opinions and emotions towards several topics ranging from political and ideological opinions to advertisement of products and services and from local news to expressing (dis-)satisfaction for events or actions.

As part of the ANIMA project, we focus on everyday discussions related to life quality around airports. The overall objective is to identify and understand these discussions then classify people's sentiments while they live, work or socialize around airports. To do this, we need to analyse discussions over an extended period of time. These are also somewhat localized since we need the involved people to either live or work around airports or to show a significant presence that would allow them to be considered as directly affected by the generated impact from the airport operation. Heathrow airport is taken as a case study to work with, as it is one of the busiest airports and is located in a highly and densely populated area. However, our proposed methodology and the described principles can be easily applied in any other similar case.

Actually, surveys assessing the impact of the operation of an airport on the population living in the adjacent areas have been carried out for a long time and have received particular focus (and a lot of scrutiny) in cases of airport expansions. These surveys have taken place in traditional ways, mainly through the selection of a representative part of the population which is contacted either by person (door-to-door), by phone or through post in order to fill a predetermined questionnaire. More recently, such surveys are being contacted either online or through mobile apps, where the invited subjects download and install an app on their mobile phones and then use the app to answer specific questions and/or allow it to monitor (parts of) their everyday life. Main disadvantages in both cases are the difficulty to extract big enough samples and to guarantee the participation of the users during the duration of the survey, since quality of life issues cannot be assessed in one-of answers. Moreover, as in all surveys, the usage of mobile apps raises various privacy concerns, which can, of course, be mitigated by extra developer effort, as it is the case in the ANIMA mobile app (described in ANIMA D3.4 to come).

Compared to these methods, surveys based on social media research and analysis exhibit various advantages and disadvantages. On the advantages side, we can put the infrastructure for capturing social media posts once and then monitor the discussions for an extended period of time with no extra cost (besides the cost of processing and storage of the posts). Additionally, social media platforms like Twitter or Facebook can provide easy access to thousands or millions of users and millions or billions of relevant tweets (depending on the airport, the area, etc.) so as extending the sample that "participates" in the survey. The users are actually taking part in online discussions based on their own interest, with no strict requirements. On the disadvantage side, online social media bring their own biases, for example it is well known that people from older generations use them very little or only for

purposes of communication with family and friends. One more problem is that posts do not necessarily carry location information, so sometimes localizing a discussion is not possible or becomes a costly operation by itself. Although, given the size of the collected information, this is a mitigated problem. Finally, discussions on social media are directly affected by whatever captures the public's eye as well as from the actual reality, for example during the recent COVID-19 crisis discussions on social media are overwhelmingly dominated by this and the lack of actual flights mitigated the issues and the discussions. The wealth of information in social media comes with several challenges. Not all opinions, posts, discussions are relevant to a specific subject so we need first to be able to extract the relevant posts or discussions. This is not a trivial subject by itself, since the definition of a subject is not exact and the way people express themselves varies greatly. Moreover, in the case of Twitter and other microblogging services it is more complicated since the imposed limit in the number of characters for each post forces people to express themselves in unique and sometimes difficult to decipher ways. Nevertheless, the number of posts that can be captured and the number of users that participate make it a viable alternative that — with the necessary scientific precautions — can provide valuable insights on the opinions and sentiments over quality-of-life issues around airports.

In order to address these challenges, a set of reusable tools and methodologies have been proposed as part of the ANIMA project. They allow capturing the necessary relevant social media posts, extracting the topics of discussions around quality of life and classifying the sentiments around these topics as positive, neutral or negative in order to depict a qualitative assessment of the opinions of people from the area around airports.

In this respect, we proposed a first approach that applies data mining and machine learning on a real time stream of public tweets to extract relevant tweets, then a lexicon-based sentiment classifier to calculate their polarities and classify them to negative, positive and neutral.

In a second approach, we attempted to deal with the effects of COVID19 on aircraft traffic and consequently on discussions about quality life around airports, by relying on historical data to do our processing. We also applied machine learning and embedding representation methods for both relevant tweets detection and opinion analysis, as an attempt to improve the accuracy of sentiment classification.

Our overall goal is to provide a **prototype** to demonstrate that this type of analysis is both possible and also provides interesting insights in the sentiments of the users that are active in the area around an airport, in an effort to understand their sentiment towards the effect the airport has to the way of life and the possible annoyance it might cause to it.

2.2 Scientific Background

The core of the work in this task is the extraction of opinions and the analysis of sentiments contained within those opinions that would allow us to classify those opinions as positive, neutral and negative.

Sentiment classification is a hard challenge that faces several challenges such as dealing with trivial posts, incomplete sentences, misspelling and abbreviations due to size restrictions, dealing with specific meanings such as irony or humour and the use of emotional expressions. Sentiment classification approaches can be classified into three main categories: (I) machine learning, (II) lexicon based and (III) hybrid approach.

2.2.1 Machine Learning-based Approach

Machine learning-based sentiment analysis consists in predicting the polarity of sentiments by training a machine-learning model with examples of emotions in text to automatically learn how to detect sentiment without human input. Related works have mostly used emoticons (Read, 2005), slangs and acronyms (Hutto et al., 2014), words in text and their respective part-of-speech (POS), which is the grammatical description of word (e.g. noun, verb, adjective, etc.), intensifiers such as all caps and characters repetitions (e.g. happpyyy) (Kouloumpis et al., 2014), punctuation marks, n-grams and negation mark as features of the analysed tweets. In their work, Read (2005) and Cortes and Vapnik (1995) performed a 2-way classification (i.e., positive or negative) on data with emoticons and applied respectively SVM (Support Vector Machine) and NB (Naive Bayes) algorithms that were able to achieve more than 70% accuracy.

Recent works tried neural networks with word embeddings for the representation of tweets and showed that they achieved much better performance in sentiment analysis (Ren et al., 2016; Jianqiang et al., 2018; Tang et al., 2015; Ouyang et al., 2015). Word embeddings consist in representing words by dense vectors with much lower dimensionality. Each word is positioned via its vector value into a multi-dimensional space (embedding space) which helps to take into account their semantics (i.e., synonyms are geometrically close, antonyms are far from each other). Mathematical operations can also be applied on vectors and produce semantically correct results. A typical example is that the sum of the word embeddings of king and female produces the word embedding of queen. Methods to generate this representation include neural networks, dimensionality reduction on the word co-occurrence matrix, probabilistic models, explainable knowledge base method, and explicit representation in terms of the context in which words appear (Selva Birunda and Kanniga Devi, 2021). In (Ren, 2016), we find a context-based convolutional neural network (CNN) to apply sentiment classification on Twitter corpus. Other works, like (Tang et al., 2015), encode sentiment information of texts (e.g., sentences and words) together with contexts of words in sentiment embeddings. They showed that sentiment embeddings consistently outperform context-based embeddings in tasks such as word-level sentiment analysis, sentence level sentiment classification and building sentiment lexicons.

2.2.2 Lexicon-based Approach

Besides machine learning approaches for sentiment classification, we found in the literature that lexicon-based approaches were also applied. While finding or constructing those lexicons is not always an easy task and the difficulty might vary depending on the language, these methods allow us to use a list of words (dictionary of subjective words), where each word is associated with a specific sentiment; emoticons are used the same way as well. (Yadollahi et al., 2017) discuss the ability to use more than one dataset to take into account multiple subjective perspectives of the word and to modify the existing dictionary in order to satisfy the topic sentiment characteristics. (Asghar et al., 2017) proposed to classify sentiments in reviews by combining an emoticon classifier, a modifier and negation classifier and a classifier based on the opinion lexicon SentiWordNetwork (SWNC) in a sequential, then input the text to a domain specific classifier (DSC) that takes into account the polarity of domain specific words both existing or unknown in SWNC.

2.2.3 Hybrid Approach

Hybrid approaches have also been reported in the literature. They consist of combining both machine learning and the lexicon-based approaches, which has the potential to improve the sentiment classification performance. As an example, Khan et al., (2014) proposed a hybrid sentiment classifier on twitter data that uses an emoticon classifier, improved polarity classifier and a SWNC. This algorithm showed a good performance on classifying tweets especially on reducing the number of neutral tweets. More information on related works in the area can be found in (Meddeb et al., 2019).

2.3 Analysis Pipeline

For our opinion classification task, we explored two main approaches: a real-time lexicon-based classification and an offline, machine learning and embedding-based classification. Both provide a processing pipeline of four distinct sequential and interdependent steps (cf. Figure 2.1). More specifically: collection and preprocessing of tweets for relevance detection, identification of relevant tweets, preprocessing of relevant tweets for sentiment analysis and sentiment analysis. The difference between the two methods is that the first was built to process tweets in real-time (so upon arrival a tweet would be classified as relevant or not and subsequently as positive, negative or neutral), while the second is built to batch process what we call “historical tweets”, namely tweets that have been collected going backwards in time and as such do not carry any real-time processing requirements. This decision was made in order to cope with the COVID-19 pandemic implications, since it became almost impossible to have relevant tweets in real-time and with the flight restrictions introduced for a long period the life around airports was not affected anymore and at the same degree by the airport noise.

Figure 2.1 : The twitter analysis pipeline (Meddeb et al., 2019).

2.4 Lexicon-based Opinion Classification

2.4.1 Collection and Preprocessing of Tweets

Tweets are collected through the Twitter API, which provides a standard way to get (a part of) the real time stream of public tweets and filter those by keywords, location, language, users, etc. We used mainly keyword-based and location-based queries. We are extracting only English language tweets and use keywords like: “Heathrow”, “LHR”, “noise”, “annoyance”, etc. to increase the chances to get relevant messages. In addition, location queries were used based on Heathrow’s day, evening and night level (L_{den}) noise contours in order to bound the area of interest. (This led to a bounding box of 167 km wide and 73 km long, centred on Heathrow airport to be used as location filter to Twitter API).

Those tweets go through a pre-processing phase, where we firstly remove links, numbers, emoticons and Twitter specific words, then we make all words lowercase and apply tokenization. On those tokenized words, we correct as many errors as possible (mainly spelling errors) and then we assign part-of-speech (POS) tags and lemmatize the words in order to work with a more compact and stronger set for understanding relevance. It should be noted here that the removed parts (e.g., emoticons) are not deleted permanently but are passed to the next processing steps.

2.4.2 Relevance Detection

From the previous step we end up with a bag of words (including hashtags), so here we use these words to form unigrams, bigrams and hashtags as features and use tf-idf as a metric to represent tweets. Then the SVM algorithm is trained on a manually annotated sample of tweets, so as to be able to classify tweets as relevant or not. We filter the relevant tweets through a lexicon-based classifier in order to benefit from the domain knowledge (expressed through the lexicon), which assigns a relevance score to each tweet. We keep those tweets that exceed a threshold ϵ . This double classification provides better results compared with other methods.

Figure. 2.2: Relevance classification flowchart (Meddeb et al., 2019).

2.4.3 Sentiment Analysis of Relevant Tweets

Based on the selection of relevant tweets, we proceed to classify those tweets as positive, negative or neutral. We do this by exploring various facets of the tweets and calculate different scores that represent each facet. At the end, we put together those scores in order to compute a single score per relevant tweet that would allow the system (based on this value) to classify it. In order to do this, we use three different facets: (a) emoticons (collected from tweets and labelled as positive or negative), (b) lexicon-based polarity of words (using dictionaries, where each word has been classified as positive or negative and given a score) and (c) the SentiWordNet, a dictionary where each word has been attributed at the same time a positive, a negative and a neutral score with the restriction that these scores add up to 1. The final weighted score is calculated based on the individual scores and is used for classifying the tweet.

Figure. 2.3. Sentiment classification flowchart (Meddeb et al., 2019).

2.4.4 Experimental Evaluation

Due to the restrictions mentioned earlier because of the COVID-19 pandemic, we were unable to collect a significant number of tweets in order to verify that the system we build performs correctly and adequately under different scenarios. The tweets that we collected suffered from a common problem in Machine Learning, which is class in balance since the collection took place before the pandemic and then when the pandemic happened it was stopped, so collecting enough (equal number of) tweets from all the classes (positive, negative and neutral) was not possible.

We managed to evaluate the system with a small number of relevant tweets (around 2000) which gave us promising results but inconclusive ones, as the reader can see in Table 2.1. We actually tried different combinations of classifiers and lexicons and experimented with the thresholds of the scoring functions results so as to classify the tweets as positive, negative and neutral. The results of such experimentation are presented in Table 2.1 and demonstrate

the different combinations we experiment with. In this Table, we evaluate the proposed (and described above) classifier (PC) against the emotion-based classifier (EmC), the lexicon (only) polarity classifier (LPC) and the SentiWordNet classifier. It is rather straightforward to conclude that our proposal outperforms the rest, existing, well-known classifiers but we did not have the chance yet to thoroughly evaluate it.

2.4.5 Analysis of results

Due to the small number of tweets involved in this experiment because of the overall world situation, we did not perform a very extensive analysis of the results. We only experimented with identifying the possibly interesting points for analysis, for example we tried to identify the temporal distribution and the spatial distribution of the tweets, as it is seen in Figure 2.4 and Figure 2.5 respectively. If there is an interest for additional discussion of the results, we would like to suggest that the reader consults the corresponding paper published by some of the authors of this deliverable (Meddeb et al., 2019).

Table. 2.1. Evaluation of the real-time lexicon based classifier (Meddeb et al., 2019).

			Confusion matrix			Metrics			
			Positive	Negative	Neutral	precision	recall	F-measure	accuracy
EmC	Thresholds	Positive	0	0	26	0 %	0 %	-	4.90 %
	$\tau_1=\tau_2=0$	Negative	3	6	592	100%	1%	1,98 %	
		Neutral	0	0	26	4.04 %	100%	7.76%	
LPC	Thresholds	Positive	10	7	9	12.50 %	38.46 %	18.86 %	62.17 %
	$\tau_1=0.027$ $\tau_2=-0.001$	Negative	66	380	155	96.69 %	63.23 %	76.46 %	
		Neutral	4	6	16	8.89 %	61.54 %	15.53 %	
SWNC	Thresholds	Positive	4	15	7	4.44 %	15.38 %	6.90 %	69.37%
	$\tau_1=0.015$	Negative	79	443	79	95.05 %	73.71 %	82.64 %	

	$\tau_2=0.005$	Neutral	7	13	6	6.52 %	23.07 %	10.17%	
PC	Thresholds	Positive	12	10	4	12.12%	46.15%	19.20 %	77.79 %
	$\theta_1=0.01$ $\theta_2=-0.001$	Negative	80	491	30	95.34 %	81.70 %	87.99 %	
	$\tau_1=0.015$ $\tau_2=0.004$	Neutral	7	14	5	12.82 %	19.23 %	15.38 %	

Figure. 2.4. Weekly Temporal Distribution of positive, negative, neutral tweets (Meddeb et al., 2019).

Figure. 2.5. Spatial distribution of positive, negative, neutral tweets (Meddeb et al., 2019).

2.5 Machine Learning and Embeddings-based Opinion Classification

2.5.1 Collection and Preprocessing of Tweets

As already discussed, due to the COVID-19 crisis and the resulting lack of flights, issues related to living next to airports and discussions about it have been mitigated. Hence, using a real time stream of public tweets does not allow the collection of sufficient amounts of relevant tweets which may, consequently, affect the subsequent sentiment analysis accuracy and the possibility to analyse those results any further.

In this respect, we took the decision to collect and work with what we call “historical twitter data” from the pre-covid period. We started by identifying interesting accounts that users living around Heathrow may be following, e.g., the Heathrow Airport account, the local authorities’ accounts and local media accounts of cities surrounding Heathrow, etc. (cf. Table 2.2). Then, we collect all tweets published by those users.

Tweets are collected through the Twitter API (the tweet timeline endpoint of twitter API version2), which provides a standard way to get all tweets of a specific user that have been published since 2008. The Tweet timeline endpoint also supports the ability to specify *start_{time}* and *end_{time}* parameters to receive tweets that were created within a certain window of time. For our processing, we collect tweets published before 2020. We succeeded in getting **70457335 tweets from 41017 users**. We also collected user comments from popular websites for visitors TripAdvisor and AirBnB. In the text, when we refer to all types of texts as tweets, since the vast majority of the collected texts comes from Twitter.

Afterwards, we filter the tweets by keywords and language. We only extract English language tweets and use keywords like “Heathrow”, “LHR”, “noise”, “annoyance”, “airport”, plane, etc. to increase the chances to get relevant messages. Then, they go through pre-processing for the relevance detection step. We firstly remove links, numbers, twitter specific words (tags and hashtags), special characters, and html elements. Then we replace emojis by textual descriptions of the emotions they describe and substitute commonly used abbreviations (e.g., replace “didn’t” by “did not”).

Due to processing limitations, we decided to reduce the number of tweets that we will use in the current study to **approximately 11000000**, which remains an adequately high number.

2.5.2 Relevance Detection

In this approach, relevance detection is mainly relying on embedding-based representation of data. Word embedding is the representation of words as dense real-valued vectors with much lower dimensionality. This representation encodes the meaning of the word. In fact, each word is positioned via its vector value into a multi-dimensional space (embedding space) and the words that are closer are expected to be similar in meaning. The main idea in relevance detection is to start by defining a description of a base relevant tweet and generate its vector representation using a word embedding. Afterwards, we generate vectors of all tweets using the same embedding and compute their similarity to the description vector. Using a similarity threshold, tweets are classified as relevant or irrelevant.

Embedding Phase

In our processing, the embedding is done using GloVe (Global Vectors for Word Representations), an unsupervised learning algorithm that uses dimensionality reduction on a word co-occurrence matrix for obtaining vector representations of words. It is trained over aggregated global word-word co-occurrence statistics from a generic corpus (wikipedia). In order to embed a tweet, we need to generate a single vector representing the whole tweet. In this respect, we simply do an average over the vectors generated for all of its composing words.

Definition of Relevant Tweets Description

Retrieved texts are saved in comma separated files (csv). Each file corresponds to a particular user. In order to define the *relevant tweets description (RTD)* and the similarity threshold we needed to manually label a dataset of randomly selected tweets. The RTD corresponds to the union of the respective texts of eight randomly selected relevant tweets, and its vector representation corresponds to the average of their vector representations. We experimented with different ways to construct the RTD, including the use of repetitions, addition of specific keywords, increasing the size and using or not hashtags. The results are very similar so finally we went with the simple combination of a set of relevant tweets that we manually identified.

Definition of similarity threshold

For our processing, the similarity of tweet vectors is evaluated using the cosine similarity (Cos_s). Mathematically, the cosine similarity measures the cosine of the angle between two vectors projected in a multi-dimensional space.

Let T be the set of all the extracted tweets t and VT be the set of their embedded representations vt such that:

$$T = \{t_1, t_2, \dots, t_n\} \quad (1)$$

$$VT = \{vt_1, vt_2, vt_3, \dots, vt_n\} \quad (2)$$

Let t_x, t_y be two tweets and vt_x and vt_y be their respective vector representations of size m such that:

$$t_x, t_y \in T \quad (3)$$

$$vt_x, vt_y \in VT \quad (4)$$

The cosine similarity of vt_x and vt_y is defined as follows:

$$Cos_s(vt_x, vt_y) = \frac{vt_x \cdot vt_y}{\|vt_x\| \|vt_y\|} = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^m vt_{xi} vt_{yi}}{\sqrt{\sum_{i=1}^m vt_{xi}^2} \sqrt{\sum_{i=1}^m vt_{yi}^2}} \quad (5)$$

The resulting similarity ranges from -1 meaning “exactly opposite”, to 1 meaning “exactly the same”, with 0 indicating orthogonality or decorrelation, while in between values indicate intermediate similarity or dissimilarity.

In order to decide whether a tweet is similar to the *RTD* and thus can be classified as relevant, we relied on a similarity threshold. To determine the similarity threshold (S_{th}), we started by randomly selecting a set of relevant tweets from our labelled dataset, then we generated their respective vector representations and calculated their respective cosine similarity values with the *RTD* vector. The median value of those similarities is then set as the similarity threshold.

Let tv_x be the embedded representation of the tweet t_x and $vRTD$ be the embedded representation of the *RTD*. The relevance class $rClass(t_x)$ of the tweet t_x is :

$$rClass(t_x) = \begin{cases} \text{Relevant} & \text{if } Cos_S(tv_x, vRTD) \geq S_{th} \\ \text{Irrelevant} & \text{Otherwise} \end{cases} \quad (6)$$

2.5.3 Sentiment Analysis of Relevant Tweets

After the relevance detection phase, relevant tweets are analyzed using a clustering based method to be classified as positive, negative and neutral.

Let RT be the set of relevant tweets rt , W be the set of words w such that:

$$RT = \{rt_1, rt_2, \dots, rt_p\} \quad (7)$$

$$W = \{w_1, w_2, \dots, w_q\} \quad (8)$$

A relevant tweet is defined by :

$$rt = \{W\}, (rt \in RT) \quad (9)$$

2.5.4 Word Sentiment Score calculation

In this step, we extract the unique words from our corpus of relevant tweets RT . Then, we establish the word sentiment score dictionary where each word of the vocabulary is associated with its sentiment score (cf. Figure 2.6).

Let VW be the set of our tweet corpus vocabulary words vw , such that:

$$VW = \{vw_1, vw_2, \dots, vw_r\}, VW \subset W \quad (10)$$

We consider two predefined lists of respectively positive words (PW) and negative words (NW). The positive score ($PosS$) of the word is the maximum value of all of its cosine similarity values with the words of the positive list. The same process is done to find its negative score ($NegS$). The sentiment score of the word (WSS) corresponds then to the difference between the positive and the negative scores:

$$WSS(vw_i) = PosS(vw_i) - NegS(vw_i) \quad (11)$$

Figure. 2.6. Word sentiment score calculation.

2.5.5 Tweet Sentiment score calculation

For each tweet, we identify four groups of words: positive words, negative words, neutral words and hashtags. The positive and negative words are those that can be found in the predefined lists PW and NW . The hashtag group contains the hashtags and the neutral group corresponds to all that remains.

For each group, we extract the word sentiment score of each word from the sentiment score dictionary, then we calculate their average. The four averages are then used to calculate an overall sentiment score of the tweet (TSS). This score corresponds to a weighted mean to which hashtags, which was decided after another series of experiments with a controlled dataset to be: negative words and positive words contribute each by 30% and the neutral words contribute by 10%.

At this point, a tweet can be classified as positive if its sentiment score is positive and as negative otherwise. In order to improve the sentiment classification, we proposed to use a clustering algorithm to identify also neutral tweets and to take into account the dynamics of the specific (each time) dataset.

2.5.6 Clustering-Based Sentiment Classification

For our clustering process, we take into account the number of words in each group. Hence our learning data corresponds to vectors of four elements: number of positive words, number of negative words, number of hashtags and the overall tweet sentiment score.

The K-means clustering algorithm (Hartigan and Wong, 1979) is then applied with $K=3$, representing the three classes we hope to identify. The positive, negative and neutral clusters are then identified based on the sentiment score values of their respective centroids. The centroid with the greatest score corresponds to the cluster of positive tweets ($PosC$), the centroid with the lowest value corresponds to the cluster of negative tweets ($NegC$) and the remaining one corresponds to the cluster of neutral tweets ($NeuC$).

The sentiment class of tweet $sClass(rt_i)$ is :

$$sClass(rt_i) = \begin{cases} \text{Positive} & \text{if } rt_i \in PosC \\ \text{Negative} & \text{if } rt_i \in NegC \\ \text{Neutral} & \text{if } rt_i \in NeuC \end{cases} \quad (12)$$

2.6 Evaluation and Results

The pipeline of the proposed approaches has been implemented in the python programming environment. In order to evaluate the performances of our classifiers, we used the confusion matrix (cf. table1) to calculate the precision, recall and f-measure metrics for each class, and also to calculate the accuracy of the model.

For example, considering the sentiment classification, precision (P), recall (R) and f-measure (F) of the positive class, as well as the accuracy of classification are defined as follows:

$$P_{pos} = \frac{T_{pos}}{F_{pos-neg} + F_{pos-neu}} \quad (13) \quad R_{pos} = \frac{T_{pos}}{F_{neg-pos} + F_{neu-pos}} \quad (14)$$

$$F_{pos} = 2 \frac{P_{pos} R_{pos}}{P_{pos} + R_{pos}} \quad (15) \quad Acc = \frac{T_{pos} + T_{neg} + T_{neu}}{AllTweets} \quad (16)$$

Using this metrics, we can compute the Confusion Matrix seen in Table 2.2 in order to be able to easily identify the overall results provided by the algorithm.

		Predicted Class		
		Positive	Negative	Neutral
Actual Class	Positive	T_{pos}	$F_{neg-pos}$	$F_{neu-pos}$
	Negative	$F_{pos-neg}$	T_{neg}	$F_{neu-neg}$
	Neutral	$F_{pos-neu}$	$F_{neg-neu}$	T_{neu}

Table 2.2. Confusion Matrix

2.6.1 Relevance Detection

We followed the standard process in training Machine Learning classifiers, in our case an unsupervised one. We evaluated the performance of the clustering process in a smaller set of data, randomly picked from the bigger dataset, which was manually annotated. We did this to create a ground-truth to be able to compare with. This also led to our choices since we experimented with different kinds of embedding (BERT, GloVe, Fair) and different kinds of similarity metrics (cosine, Manhattan, Minkowski distance). We also experimented on the level at which we would like to apply the method: do we stay at the word level (using word embedding) or move the compare at the sentence or the document level. After a lot of experiments, we concluded that the best fitting method will be working at the document level (where each tweet is considered a document), using Fair embedding and cosine similarity. The cumulative results are shown in Table 2.3.

Confusion Matrix	Metrics
------------------	---------

		Relevant	Irrelevant	Precision	Recall	F-measure	Accuracy
ECC (D2)	Relevant	123	12	72%	78%	75%	74%
	Irrelevant	25	122	76%	69%	72%	

Table 2.3. Confusion Matrix for the testing dataset.

The results of the experiments are quite promising and the accuracy level (74%) is at an acceptable level, given the complexity of the subject.

2.6.2 Sentiment Analysis

In order to evaluate the performance of the lexicon-based classifier (LC), we manually labelled a dataset (D1) from a real time tweet stream. D1 counts 653 tweets with 26 corresponding to each of the positive and neutral classes and 601 corresponding to the negative class.

For the embedding and clustering based classification, we used an evaluation dataset (D2) of 1000 labelled relevant tweets. It consists of 191 positive tweets, 385 negative tweets, and 424 neutral tweets.

			Confusion Matrix			Metrics			
			Positive	Negative	Neutral	Precision	Recall	F-measure	Accuracy
LC (D1)	Thresholds	Positive	12	10	4	12.12%	46/15%	19.20%	77.79%
	$\theta_1 = 0.01,$ $\theta_2 = 0.001,$ $\tau_1 = 0.015,$ $\tau_2 = 0$	Negative	80	491	30	95.34%	81.70%	87.99%	
		Neutral	7	14	5	12.82%	19.23%	15.38%	
ECC (D2)	--	Positive	53	16	122	52%	28%	36%	66%
		Negative	7	307	71	75%	80%	77%	
		Neutral	41	87	296	61%	70%	65%	

Table 2.4. Confusion Matrix for the testing dataset.

Our sentiment analysis method was applied on over 687487 relevant tweets. To those, we applied our embedding and clustering based classification and had 135860 tweets classified as positive, 433698 as negative, and 117929 as neutral.

Spatial Analysis

In order to provide spatial insights about the distribution of sentiments, we generated maps and charts that depict, that help us to explore the possible distributions of negative tweets (namely, annoyance) around the airport and correlate this to the size of the district, the distance from the airport and the positioning in the noise contours.

The first two maps illustrate the spatial distribution and density of the users who are the origin of the analysed tweets, both by city (Figure 2.7) and district (Figure 2.8). As we can observe,

there is a widespread distribution from the communities around the airport, including many communities that are outside the noise contours.

Figure 2.7. Spatial distribution of users by city

Figure 2.8. Spatial distribution of users by district

If we correlate this information with the spatial distribution and density of the negative tweets (Figure 2.9), we can observe that there is a rather strong correlation with the distance (as expected) but on the other hand, communities like “Kingston upon Thames” which are outside the noise contours and in a medium distance from the airport exhibit a strong negative behaviour (namely expressing annoyance), which is a rather surprising result that requires further local investigation. We need especially to further investigate, what are the specific local characteristics that possibly increase the annoyance in this community in comparison to communities in its immediate neighbourhood, which are even closer to the airport and the noise contours.

Figure 2.9. Distribution of negative tweets per City

In an effort to understand the possible correlations with the distributions of the sentiment of the tweets, we generated Figure 2.10, which provides the distribution of tweets by sentiments per district. Since Heathrow is located 3 miles (4.8 km) west of the town of Hounslow (Hounslow borough), 3 miles south of Hayes (Hillingdon borough), and 3 miles north-east of Staines-upon-Thames (Spelthorne districts), we grouped tweets by those districts. We then generated, for each, a pie graph giving: the number of negative tweets, highlighted in red in the map, the number of positive tweets and the number of neutral tweets. We were not able to observe any significant variations in the distributions, which means that the ratio of positive vs. negative opinions does not change significantly with distance.

Figure 2.10. Distribution of tweets per sentiment per District

Temporal Analysis

We also tried to observe correlations in the data in the temporal axis and we tried to analyse behaviours with regard to the time. In Figure 2.11, we can observe the evolution of the number and distribution of opinions for the last 4 years of the data. This shows a clear increase every year and with a steady pace of the involvement of people in the discussions concerning the effect of the airport on their lives. On the other hand, the ratio between positive and negative tweets seems to be preserved.

Figure 2.12, gives us the distribution of the tweets by polarity during the year and per month. Here we can observe a clear increase of negative tweets during the 3rd and the 8th month of the year. This finding deserves further investigation to understand if it is correlated with the increase in the traffic during these months due to the beginning and end of the touristic period. The data we collected was insufficient by itself to allow us to explore this.

Finally, in Figure 2.13, we looked into the difference in the sentiment of people between days during the week and the weekend. We selected data from the last year of our data collection (2019) and focused on and compared two months: August, which has the highest number of tweets and December, which has the lowest number of tweets. As we can easily observe, while the overall activity is, as expected, lower during the weekends, the ratio between negative and positive tweets increases during the non-working days. This is an expected result that verifies that people during the week will get less annoyed because they might be exposed to the annoyance for a shorter period of time due to their absence from home to work. We need to further analyse this finding to better understand the hourly distribution of the negative tweets so as to verify the connection to the moving of people due to work. We can

correlate this result with the mobility maps described in the first part of this deliverable on dynamic noise maps.

Figure 2.11. Temporal distribution of sentiments over the period from 2016 to 2019

Figure 2.12. Temporal distribution of sentiments by month throughout 2019

Figure 2.13. Comparison of sentiments between weekdays (work days) and weekends for December and August 2019.

2.7 Conclusions

In this part of the deliverable, we presented two methodologies to capture and analyse tweets, either in (i) real-time or (2) offline. The two methods can actually be further developed to work together. Both methods capture posts from social media and other sites with user-generated content and after deciding on whether it is relevant or not to the annoyance discussion, they classify it as expressing positive, negative or neutral sentiments. We followed up with a spatiotemporal analysis of the distribution of the tweets. We were able to collect and analyse a rather considerable set of posts (around 11 million tweets), that span a period close to a decade.

Our analysis has revealed a consistent overall behaviour but has also highlighted some local exceptions that require further investigation, with the need to expand the collection of the local datasets. We verified the (negative) correlation between the negative sentiment and the distance from the airport and the noise contours, with some notable exceptions. It is also important to note here that the ratio of positive vs. negative statements remains rather stable with regard to the distance.

The temporal analysis has verified the overall increase in tweets (so an increased citizen concern) over the years and has revealed some spikes during some months of the same year,

again in a consistent manner over the years. Further investigation is needed to explore the reasons for this behaviour and correlate it with other airport activities.

As mentioned in the beginning, the effort here was to build a **working prototype** that shows that:

- we can use social media and other user generated content in web sites to chart the sentiment of people about the possible annoyance caused by the airport activities in their lives
- we can extract an adequate number of posts, that allow us to work with some certainty for our results, although further analysis is needed to explore bias in the data and to be able to generalize the conclusions
- we draw results based on the comparison internally of the data and we do not try at the moment to correlate with external sources
- we built a toolkit that is able to analyse posts both in real-time and offline and provide insights towards the users' feelings; this toolkit is not tied to a specific airport or even a specific language. We can use it to collect and analyse information and generate visualizations of this information. We plan to release this toolkit as open source in the near future to allow other studies to be conducted in the same manner.

The work can be further expanded to take into account additional information from the area under investigation and the results can be also compared with other studies using more traditional tools like in person surveys or surveys based on mobile apps. In ANIMA, this work is part of the greater ecosystem of methods and tools that are provided in order to study annoyance as it is expressed by the users (residents, visitors, etc.) that are interacting and affected by the airport on a daily basis.

References

- Asghar, M.Z., Khan, A., Ahmad, S., Qasim, M., Khan, I.A. (2017) Lexicon-enhanced sentiment analysis framework using rule-based classification scheme. PloS one 12(2), e0171649.
- Barbosa, H., Barthelemy, M., Ghoshal, G., James, C. R., Lenormand, M., Louail, T., Menezes, R., Ramasco, J. J., Simini, F., & Tomasini, M. (2018). Human mobility: Models and applications. Physics Reports, 734, 1–74. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.physrep.2018.01.001>
- Benocci, R., Bellucci, P., Peruzzi, L., Bisceglie, A., Angelini, F., Confalonieri, C., & Zambon, G. (2019). Dynamic Noise Mapping in the Suburban Area of Rome (Italy). Environments, 6(7). <https://doi.org/10.3390/environments6070079>
- Castiglione, J., Bradley, M., & Gliebe, J. (2014). Activity-Based Travel Demand Models: A Primer. In Activity-Based Travel Demand Models: A Primer. Transportation Research Board. <https://doi.org/10.17226/22357>

Civil Aviation Authority. (2019). Heathrow Airport 2018 Summer Noise Contours and Noise Action Plan Contours, ERCD Report 1901. Civil Aviation Authority. https://www.heathrow.com/file_source/HeathrowNoise/Static/Heathrow_NAP_Contours_2016_and_Summer_Contours_2016.pdf

Cortes, C., Vapnik, V. (1995) Support-vector networks. *Machine learning* 20(3), 273–297.

D'Hondt, E., Stevens, M., & Jacobs, A. (2013). Participatory noise mapping works! An evaluation of participatory sensing as an alternative to standard techniques for environmental monitoring. *Pervasive and Mobile Computing*, 9(5), 681–694. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.pmci.2012.09.002>

Department for Transport. (2021). National Travel Survey, 2002-2020: Special Licence Access. [data collection]. 10th Edition. UK Data Service. SN: 7553, <http://doi.org/10.5255/UKDA-SN-7553-10>

Drosatos, G., Efraimidis, P. S., Athanasiadis, I. N., Stevens, M., & D'Hondt, E. (2014). Privacy-preserving computation of participatory noise maps in the cloud. *Journal of Systems and Software*, 92(1), 170–183. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jss.2014.01.035>

DYNAMAP. (2014). <http://www.life-dynamap.eu/project/>

ECAC. (2016). ECAC/CEAC Doc 29 4th Edition Report on Standard Method of Computing Noise Contours around Civil Airports Volume 2: Technical Guide (Vol. 2, Issue December). <https://www.ecac-ceac.org/documents/10189/51566/02.+Doc29+4th+Edition+Volume+2.pdf/d9164c10-339a-4650-ba87-6540cd68e4a9>

European Commission. (2002). Position paper on dose response relationships between transportation noise and annoyance.

European Commission Working Group on Health and Socio-Economic Aspects. (2004). Position paper on dose-effect relationships for night time noise (Issue November).

Ganić, E., & Babić, O. (2017, July). Air Traffic Assignment to Reduce Population Noise Exposure: An Approach Incorporating Human Mobility Patterns. 21st Air Transport Research Society World Conference.

Ganić, E., Babić, O., Čangalović, M., & Stanojević, M. (2018). Air traffic assignment to reduce population noise exposure using activity-based approach. *Transportation Research Part D: Transport and Environment*, 63, 58–71. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.trd.2018.04.012>

Ganić, E., Babić, O., Čangalović, M., & Stanojević, M. (2017). Air traffic assignment to reduce population noise exposure: an approach incorporating human mobility patterns. *XLIV International Symposium on Operational Research*, 746–751.

Ganić, E., Ho-Huu, V., Babić, O., & Hartjes, S. (2018). Air traffic assignment to reduce population noise exposure and fuel consumption using multi-criteria optimisation. *Proceedings of the 26th International Conference Noise and Vibration*, 69–76. <https://www.znrfak.ni.ac.rs/noise2018/Proceedings.html>

- Ganić, E., van Oosten, N., Meliveo, L., Jeram, S., Louf, T., & Ramasco, J. J. (2020). Dynamic noise maps for Ljubljana airport. 10th SESAR Innovation Days.
- Girardin, F., Calabrese, F., Fiore, F. D., Ratti, C., & Blat, J. (2008). Digital Footprinting: Uncovering Tourists with User-Generated Content. *IEEE Pervasive Computing*, 7(4), 36–43. <https://doi.org/10.1109/MPRV.2008.71>
- Hartigan, J. A., & Wong, M. A. (1979). Algorithm AS 136: A K-Means Clustering Algorithm. *Journal of the Royal Statistical Society. Series C (Applied Statistics)*, 28(1), 100–108. <https://doi.org/10.2307/2346830>
- Ho-Huu, V., Ganić, E., Hartjes, S., Babić, O., & Curran, R. (2019). Air traffic assignment based on daily population mobility to reduce aircraft noise effects and fuel consumption. *Transportation Research Part D: Transport and Environment*, 72, 127–147. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.trd.2019.04.007>
- Hutto, C., Gilbert, E. (2014) Vader: A parsimonious rule-based model for sentiment analysis of social media text. In: *Proceedings of the International AAAI Conference on Web and Social Media*, vol. 8.
- Jianqiang, Z., Xiaolin, G., Xuejun, Z. (2018) Deep convolution neural networks for twitter sentiment analysis. *IEEE Access* 6, 23253–23260 . DOI 10.1109/ACCESS.2017.2776930.
- Khan, F.H., Bashir, S., Qamar, U. (2014) Tom: Twitter opinion mining framework using hybrid classification scheme. *Decision support systems* 57, 245–257.
- Kouloumpis, E., Wilson, T., Moore, J. (2011) Twitter sentiment analysis: The good, the bad and the omg! In: *Proceedings of the International AAAI Conference on Web and Social Media*, vol. 5.
- Kozielecki, P., & Czyzewski, A. (2008). An application for vector-based dynamic noise maps generation. *Joint Baltic-Nordic Acoustics Meeting*. <https://citeseerx.ist.psu.edu/viewdoc/download?doi=10.1.1.631.6764&rep=rep1&type=pdf>
- Mcardle, G., Furey, E., Lawlor, A., & Pozdnoukhov, A. (2014). Using Digital Footprints for a City-Scale Traffic Simulation. *ACM Transactions on Intelligent Systems and Technology*, 5(3), 1–16. <https://doi.org/10.1145/2517028>
- McArdle, G., Lawlor, A., Furey, E., & Pozdnoukhov, A. (2012). City-scale traffic simulation from digital footprints. *Proceedings of the ACM SIGKDD International Workshop on Urban Computing - UrbComp '12*, 47. <https://doi.org/10.1145/2346496.2346505>
- Meddeb, I., Lavandier, C., Kotzinos, D. (2019) Using twitter streams for opinion mining: a case study on airport noise. In: *International Workshop on Information Search, Integration, and Personalization*, pp. 145–160. Springer.
- Mishra, R. K., Nair, K., Kumar, K., & Shukla, A. (2021). Dynamic noise mapping of road traffic in an urban city. *Arabian Journal of Geosciences*, 14(2). <https://doi.org/10.1007/s12517-020-06373-9>

- Ouyang, X., Zhou, P., Li, C.H., Liu, L. (2015) Sentiment analysis using convolutional neural network. In: 2015 IEEE International Conference on Computer and Information Technology; Ubiquitous Computing and Communications; Dependable, Autonomic and Secure Computing; Pervasive Intelligence and Computing, pp. 2359–2364 . DOI 10.1109/CIT/IUCC/DASC/PICOM.2015.349.
- Poslončec-Petrić, V., Šlabek, L., & Frangeš, S. (2016). With the Crowdsourced Spatial Data Collection to Dynamic Noise Map of the City of Zagreb. International Symposium on Engineering Geodesy SIG 2016, 411–423. <https://www.bib.irb.hr/822774>
- Read, J. (2005) Using emoticons to reduce dependency in machine learning techniques for sentiment classification. In: Proceedings of the ACL student research workshop, pp. 43–48.
- Ren, Y., Zhang, Y., Zhang, M., Ji, D. (2016) Context-sensitive twitter sentiment classification using neural network. In: Proceedings of the AAAI Conference on Artificial Intelligence, vol. 30.
- Selva Birunda, S., Kanniga Devi, R. (2021) A review on word embedding techniques for text classification. In: J.S. Raj, A.M. Ilyasu, R. Bestak, Z.A. Baig (eds.) Innovative Data Communication Technologies and Application, pp. 267–281. Springer Singapore, Singapore.
- Simón Otegui, L., García Morales, R., Ausejo Prieto, M., Esteban Cantera, M., Arias Salve, R., Arias Puga, J. E., & Sánchez Rivera, J. M. (2019). Dynamic Noise Map based on permanent monitoring network and street categorization. INTER-NOISE and NOISE-CON Congress and Conference Proceedings, 259(2), 7270–7281.
- Statistical Office of the Republic of Slovenia. (2019). Methodological Explanation Daily Passenger Mobility.
- Tang, D., Wei, F., Qin, B., Yang, N., Liu, T., Zhou, M. (2015) Sentiment embeddings with applications to sentiment analysis. IEEE transactions on knowledge and data Engineering 28(2), 496–509.
- Transport for London. (2011). Travel in London, supplementary report: London Travel Demand Survey (LTDS).
- Transport for London. (2019). Travel in London report 12.
- WHO. (2018). WHO Environmental Noise Guidelines for the European Region. World Health Organization Regional Office for Europe.
- Yadollahi, A., Shahraki, A.G., Zaiane, O.R. (2017) Current state of text sentiment analysis from opinion to emotion mining. ACM Computing Surveys (CSUR) 50(2), 1–33.